

**Written Brief to:
The Subcommittee on International Human Rights of the Standing Committee on Foreign
Affairs and International Development**

Regarding the study on the human rights situation in Sudan.

The effects of gender-based violence on ethnic cleansing of territory and land rights

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Introduction

This brief follows on testimony provided to the Subcommittee on International Human Rights regarding the current situation in Sudan, with a focus on events in Darfur.

The Darfur theatre of the current Sudanese war is marked by ethnic cleansing pursued as a strategy of gaining territorial control, with gender-based violence playing a central role—similar to the previous (2003–2010) conflict in Darfur (Abdul-Jalil and Unruh 2013; UN Women 2025). In the current war gender-based violence is not only a human rights violation and a war crime but also a territorial control and land governance tactic. In 2025, rape, abduction and other gender-based abuses are frequently reported in areas taken over by the paramilitary Rapid Support Forces (RSF). A number of sources report gender-based violence (GBV) taking place at a significantly large-scale, both in combat zones and in areas of displacement including displacement camps, thus revealing its use as a purposeful weapon in the war (eg., MSF 2024; The Lancet 2025; OHCHR 2015).

This brief provides an overview of the mechanisms by which GBV currently underway in Darfur acts to permanently sever the connections between women and housing, land and property (HLP) rights, thereby facilitating *permanent* territorial gains and control by RSF forces and affiliates, even when the war comes to an end and dislocated populations attempt to return to home areas. The brief then provides recommendations for the Government of Canada.

Mechanisms of ethnic cleansing and land dispossession operated through GBV

Gender-based violence functions as a highly effective forced displacement tactic in Sudan, with rape or the prospect of rape creating immediate flight from homes, leaving behind possessions, documents and witnesses important to attaching women to home areas (eg., Unruh and Abdul-Jalil 2012). HLP rights in Darfur flow through kinship and lineage structures, which for women means land and property access through marriage, HLP inheritance through maternal lines, and residence-based claims tied to household continuity (Abdul-Jalil and Unruh 2013). Because GBV disrupts these structures, survivors of GBV often cannot return to home areas due to stigma, trauma or continuing threat. Female-headed households in particular lose evidence of HLP rights, occupancy, usufruct claims and HLP-related inheritance. In addition, targeted rape and abduction of women from certain ethnic groups terrorizes whole communities and severs kinship, lineage and reproductive continuity — all of which are important to HLP claims,

attachment to home areas, and the prospect of returning to areas of origin after the war (UNSCPPHR 2025).

More specifically, because land rights operate in a customary tenure arrangement for local communities in Darfur (meaning largely undocumented), what this means for women is that HLP rights and claims are established and maintained via forms of ‘social witnessing’, such as neighbours who recognize and respect occupancy; elders who remember HLP inheritance, allocation and marriage; and women’s peer networks who attest to occupancy, residence, cultivation and use (Abdul-Jalil and Unruh 2013). Gender-based violence disrupts this evidentiary base in critical ways. The violence causes women to flee as individuals, not as intact households, thus fragmenting their place in household and community-based claims and attachments to HLP. The killing and disappearance of husbands and male relatives also contributes to leaving women without recognized advocates and intermediaries in such lineage-based tenure systems, and leaves them without a recognized social status that is needed for HLP rights their societies. Thus even when women hold legitimate HLP rights, the bridge of relations that made these rights real, collapses (Unruh 2012). And once women have suffered forced dislocation and lineage and social disruption, they can then become further vulnerable to GBV. This occurs as displaced women in camp environments face survival sex, exploitation by combatants and coerced labor or marriage (MSF 2024).

In any HLP restitution process subsequent to the end of the war, women subjected to GBV will face significant obstacles to regaining HLP rights and hence being able to return home areas. Because the stigma associated with GBV means women often avoid returning to areas of origin, this means they will be physically absent during a restitution processes—with such absence potentially interpreted administratively as a lack of claim instead of forced dislocation. And with other community members deceased, displaced or dispersed, the oral chain of HLP memory regarding who belongs where, collapses. This leaves women affected by such conditions without rights to their HLP and unable to return home. In addition, GBV produces trauma and fear that precludes engagement with restitution bureaucracy and authorities.

Summary

The gendered nature of certain forms of violence in the Sudanese war erases women's HLP claims by destroying social witnesses, disrupting inheritance and lineage continuity, and undermining women's ability to document or later assert ownership within male-biased restitution frameworks. As a result, GBV in Darfur should be understood as an integral component of ethnic cleansing that produce durable alterations to land control and ownership patterns which will persist beyond active hostilities and complicate post-conflict restitution and justice efforts. Thus GBV not only removes women from their homes and lands, it removes the means by which their relationship to HLP can later be proven. This is why GBV functions as a land-clearing technology.

Recommendations

1. In order for gender-based violence in the Sudan war to be understood as more broadly relevant than a singular human rights/war crime protection and prosecution issue, and to shape broader legal and policy responses, GAC programming should explicitly link the occurrence of GBV to

forced displacement, land grabbing, territorial control, attempts at permanent ethnic cleansing, and the inability to return home after the war.

2. GAC should be directed to expand their sanctions targeting beyond ‘direct perpetrators’ to include the enablers of forced displacement and ethnic cleansing given that these are achieved via the tactics of GBV. This can include those who finance forced displacement and ethnic cleansing; and commercial facilitators (individuals and organizations) and their networks and constituencies who seek to benefit from lands and resources (eg., gold fields, agricultural lands, etc.) as a result of forced displacement (eg Unruh 2022; Unruh and Abdul-Jalil 2014).

3. GAC should be urged to work with international partners to prioritize practical HLP restitution tools that make women’s HLP claims viable in a restitution process. These can include: violence-sensitive claims intake (female workers; confidentiality and trauma sensitive interviewing; and corroboration techniques that attend to the situation of women subjected to GBV such as neighbour testimony, woman’s network testimony, and community mapping that does not require formal title).

4. GAC should work with partners to derive a system for preserving evidence attesting to the existence of the GBV-forced displacement nexus. This can take the form of a Canadian led or a UN mandated facility for storing testimonies, incidents and forced displacement patterns in ways that are usable for subsequent HLP restitution efforts.

5. The Government of Canada should adopt the position that any restitution—reconstruction—stabilization effort should avoid, 1) legitimizing secondary occupation, 2) reconstruction that solidifies demographic change, and 3) using documentary evidence standards that discriminate against victims of GBV as part of forced displacement.

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